

ARCH50030 Professionalization

Course description

This module has been developed to help prepare School of Archaeology PhD students for their professional careers post-PhD through exploring potential career trajectories, articulating academic and transferable skillsets, honing professional skills, and developing key academic job market materials. The module is also designed to foster community amongst the postgraduates through a collaborative approach to peer review and mentorship. Students may begin the module with a set of materials already drafted or at the start of their preparations for the job search. The module will cover topics including conferences and networking, grant applications, academic publishing and peer review, public speaking and presentation of research, developing a sense of the range of career possibilities within and beyond academic archaeology, assembling core academic job documents, preparing for professional interviews, and developing good writing practices.

Learning Outcomes

At the end of the module, students should be able to:

- Identify and develop key academic skills and knowledge
- Understand the parameters of the academic and non-academic job market in archaeology
- Develop a portfolio of core job documents and create a public academic profile
- Articulate their research in a concise and engaging way

Assessments

The module is Pass/Fail. The two assessments are designed to give you the opportunity to develop core aspects of a professional portfolio develop and practice key professional skills, while receiving feedback from SoA staff. Assessments will include:

Name	Due date	Description
Professional portfolio	6 November 2024	Your portfolio will include: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Professional website• Cover letter• Updated and formatted academic CV or resume
Mock interview	Week 12	Mock Zoom interview for postdoc or professional position.

Topics by Week

Week	Dates 2024	Topic of Week	UCD Staff
1	11 September	Introduction + conferences and networking	Jess Beck
2	18 September	Job documents and professional websites	Jess Beck
3	25 September	OPEN WEEK NO CLASS: Students work on job documents	
4	2 October	Research presentation and public speaking	Jess Beck Liz Bruton
5	7 October	Postdocs	Mark Haughton Kate Kanne Ryan Lash Meriel McClatchie
6	16 October	Grant applications	Jessica Smyth Barry Molloy
7	23 October	OPEN WEEK	
8	30 October	SoA Reading Week	
9	6 November	Publishing and peer review	Jess Beck
10	13 November	Alumni Careers Panel	TBD
11	20 November	Writing, productivity, and time management	Jess Beck
12	25 November	Practice Zoom interviews	Panel TBD

ARCH50300 2024: Readings

Week 1: Introduction, Conference Presentations, and Networking

Essential

Brami, M., Emra, S., Muller, A., Preda-Bălănică, B., Irvine, B., Milić, B., Malagó, A., Meheux, K. & Fernández-Götz, M. (2023). A precarious future: reflections from a survey of early career researchers in archaeology. *European Journal of Archaeology*, 26(2), 226–250. <https://doi.org/10.1017/eea.2022.41>.

Optional

Mackie, M., & Rockwell, H. (2023). Beyond market share: Accounting for doctoral program size in recent rates of anthropology faculty job placement. *PLoS One*. 18(5): e0285330. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0285330>.

Speakman, R. J., Hadden, C. S., Colvin, M. H., Cramb, J., Jones, K. C., Jones, T. W., Kling, C. L., Lulewicz, I., Napora, K. G., Reinberger, K. L., Ritchison, B. T., Rivera-Araya, M. J., Smith, A. K., & Thompson, V. D. (2018a). Choosing a path to the ancient world in a modern market: The reality of faculty jobs in archaeology. *American Antiquity* 83,1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aaq.2017.36>.

Kawa, N. C., Clavijo Michelangeli, J. A., Clark, J. L., Ginsberg, D., & McCarty, C. (2019). The social network of US academic anthropology and its inequalities. *American Anthropologist*, 121(1), 14–29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13158>.

Please note that the Kelsky reading below on t-t (tenure-track) job searches is specific to North America, where the job market cycle is traditionally quite rigidly seasonal. This is not the case for Europe or the UK, where job ads are rolling, posted throughout the year. I advise skimming this chapter, however, because it offers a better sense of how complex the process of developing a new line can be, at both the School, College, and institutional level. Jobs do not spring forth out of the ground like mushrooms—there is an infrastructure undergirding all of this.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter four: The tenure track job search process explained. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp.31–37.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter twenty: How to work the conference. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp.123–132.

Week 2: Job Documents

Essential

Before we meet this week, read the following chapters from this book, which provides an excellent and thorough overarching guide to professional presentation and the academic job search:

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter nine: Why they want to reject you. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 65–58.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter twenty-one: The academic skepticism principle. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 133–139.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter twenty-two: What’s wrong with your cover letter. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 140–150.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter twenty-three: Tailoring with dignity. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 151–155.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter twenty-four: Rules of the academic CV. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 156–163.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter Forty-two: Managing your online presence. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 278–282.

Please also visit my website (<http://www.jessbeck.org/>) and take a look at my [CV](#) and my [sample cover letter](#) to begin familiarizing yourself with the formats of these documents. We will read a sample of real documents from some of my colleagues next meeting that will help demonstrate the variability in and broad expectations of this genre of writing.

Optional

Those of you who are planning on applying to teaching positions should familiarize yourself with what are variously called “teaching statements,” “teaching philosophy statements” and “statements of teaching philosophy. The Center for Research on Learning & Teaching (CRLT) at the University of Michigan has a helpful occasional paper that will introduce you to the format and expectations of this document.

O’Neal, C., Meizlish, D., & Kaplan, M. (2007). [Writing a statement of teaching philosophy for the academic job search](#). *Ann Arbor: University of Michigan*.

The CRLT has also compiled a helpful list of examples of teaching statements written by PhD students at Michigan. It is worth having a look through the listed disciplines to see if there is any overlap with your research interests, and skimming a couple of examples.

<https://crlt.umich.edu/tstrategies/tstpum>

Curious about how awful academic job ads can really be? Look no further. A series of junior academics organized a competition in which they sent the “winning” institution a plaque.

Dennis, D., Docot, D., Gendron, D., & Gershon, I. (2022). The worst of anthro job ads for 2021. *American Anthropologist*, 124(4), 900-905. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13781>

Souleles also writes evocatively about the inequity baked into even the most transparent European academic job searches here:

Souleles, D. (2021, October). The only lesson is that there aren't enough jobs. *Allegra lab: Anthropology for radical optimism*. <https://allegralaboratory.net/the-only-lesson-is-that-there-arent-enough-jobs/?print=pdf>

Week 4: Research presentations and public speaking

Essential

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter five: Stop acting like a grad student! In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 38–45.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter thirty-four: The job talk. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 234–239.

Optional

Purrington, C. (2019). Designing conference posters. Professional website. Accessed 14 September 2024. <https://colinpurrington.com/tips/poster-design>

Week 5: Postdocs

No readings.

Week 6: Grant applications

Essential

Bol, T., De Vaan, M., & van de Rijt, A. (2018). The Matthew effect in science funding. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(19), 4887–4890.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter seventeen: Why you want and need grants. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp.110–113.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter fifty-two: Proving your project is worthy. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 345–348.

Week 9: Publishing and Peer Review

Essential

Clauset, A. (2022, October). “How to be a good reviewer.” Twitter.
<https://twitter.com/aaronclauset/status/1576944725554171906>

Docot, D. (2022). Dispirited away: The peer review process. *PoLAR: Political and Legal Anthropology Review* 45(1): 124–128.

Souleles, D. (2020, September). What to do with the predator in your bibliography. *Allegra lab: Anthropology for Radical Optimism*. <https://allegralaboratory.net/what-to-do-with-the-predator-in-your-bibliography/>

Optional

Curious about the prestige hierarchy that operates in archaeological publishing? I’ve done some research on that.

Beck, J., Gjesfjeld, E., & Chrisomalis, S. (2021). Prestige or perish: publishing decisions in academic archaeology. *American Antiquity*, 86(4), 669-695.

As with the Clauset guidelines above, the paper below provides a synopsis of what differentiates “good” versus “bad” reviewer feedback. I recommend reading this before your next turn as a reviewer, with the caveat that a core and inexplicable assumption of the paper is that all peer reviews are conducted in English for English-language journals.

Chong, S. W., & Lin, T. (2024). Feedback practices in journal peer-review: a systematic literature review. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 49(1), 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2022.2164757>

This article outlines the peer review process step-by-step. I recommend reading the sections “An Overview of the Peer Review Process” (2–3) for an description of the stages and actors involved in the review of a submitted manuscript: it is more complex than you might think. Like Clauset and Chong & Lin, these authors also offer recommendations for strong reviews. Helpfully, they provide an actual example of a decision letter and reviewer feedback at the end of the paper.

Lovejoy, T. I., T. A. Revenson, and C. R. France. (2011). Reviewing manuscripts for peer-review journals: A primer for novice and seasoned reviewers. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine: A Publication of the Society of Behavioral Medicine* 42 (1): 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-011-9269-x>

Another popular and relatively recent article on best practices for peer-review, this time coming from industrial and organizational psychology.

Köhler, T., González-Morales, M. G., Banks, G. C., O’Boyle, E. H., Allen, J. A., Sinha, R., ... & Gulick, L. M. (2020). Supporting robust, rigorous, and reliable reviewing as the cornerstone of our profession: Introducing a competency framework for peer review. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 13(1), 1–27.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2019.121>.

Week 10: Alumni Careers Panel

There are no readings for today's meeting. Please look up the profiles of panel participants, if possible, and prepare at least three questions, either for individual participants or the panel as a whole. I will be paying attention to who has asked questions, and will mercilessly call on those who have not.

However, please do read the following resources over Week 10 and Week 11 to help you prepare for your mock Zoom interview in two weeks' time:

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter six: The attributes of a competitive tenure track candidate. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp.46–51.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter thirteen: Why “yourself” is the last person you should be. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 86–90.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter thirty: Academic job interview basics. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp.199–206.

Kelsky, K. (2015). Chapter thirty-one: The key questions in an academic interview. In *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press, pp. 207–221.

Finally, I have provided a list of all of the long-list (i.e. Zoom) interview questions I have ever been asked by search committees. This can be found under the Resources tab on my website, under “Resources for graduate students and Early Career Researchers”.

Beck, Jess. Long-list interview questions. www.jessbeck.org.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7055228>.

Read these questions, print them out, annotate them, familiarize yourselves with the broad themes, and think about how they intersect with the categories outlined in Kelsky Chapter Thirty.

Week 11: Writing, productivity, and time management

Essential

A classic. I come back to this at least once every six months.

Lamott, A. (2005) 'Shitty first drafts', In Eschholz, P., Rosa, A., and Clark, V., *Language awareness: readings for college writers*, 9 edn. Boston, Bedford/St. Martin's, pp.93–96.

I have shared these two Silvia chapters with academic writing groups I am a part of. Silvia has the capacity to get to the heart of excuses and rationalisations about writing, and help you tackle procrastination and packed schedules to make the most of your writing time. The whole book is a snappy, easy read—highly recommended.

Silvia, P. (2019). Specious barriers to writing a lot. In *How to write a lot: a practical guide to productive academic writing*, 2nd edn. Washington D.C., American Psychological Association, pp.11–27.

Silvia, P. (2019). The care and feeding of writing schedules. In *How to write a lot: a practical guide to productive academic writing*, 2nd edn. Washington D.C., American Psychological Association, pp.29–46.

Optional

A colleague recommended this book to me during my first year at UCD. While I have not made my way through the whole Belcher method, the overall strategy—a commitment to a short, but daily and *routine* short stint of writing, has been working well for me lately. Please note, though I have provided the entire chapter, all you need to read is pp. 1–10 and 18–41!

Belcher, W. L. (2009). Week 1: Designing your plan for writing. In *Writing your journal article in 12 weeks: a guide to academic publishing success*, Los Angeles, Sage, pp. 1–41.

Week 12: Practice zoom interviews

No readings. Schedule TBD.

General Recommended Readings and Resources

These books provide useful general references for academic writing, productivity, and research design. I've read many of these books myself over the last few years while seeking to refine my own approaches to writing and time management. To compile this list, I've also solicited advice from colleagues who have taught university writing classes or similar research design modules at other institutions. Where possible, I have linked to the UCD library page to make it easier for you to find these resources and noted when specific volumes are available as e-books. Happy reading!

Beck, J. (2024). Professional website. www.jessbeck.org.

My website includes a relatively current copy of my CV, as well as resources for graduate students. These include job documents from successful applications (including a sample cover letter, research statement, teaching statement, and teaching portfolio) and academic job interview prep and advice. The latter category includes questions for every long-list interview I've ever had (N=12) and wrote up a short document detailing the practical advice I wish I had had before my first campus visits.

Belcher, W. (2019) [Writing your journal article in twelve weeks: a guide to academic publishing success](#), 2nd edn. Chicago, University of Chicago Press.

This book is particularly useful for anyone considering publishing their thesis after achieving their MSc. Belcher's tips on writing practice are thoughtful and accessible, and she provides many writing accountability templates and useful advice on structuring your time.

Booth, W. C. et al. (2016). [The craft of research](#), 4th edn. Chicago, University of Chicago Press.

This volume provides a structured guide to thinking through the steps of research design and project structure. The entire book is available as an e-book in the UCD library should you wish to peruse it further.

Fogelin, L. (2019). *An unauthorized companion to American archaeological theory*. Available at

[https://www.academia.edu/40368858/An Unauthorized Companion to American Archaeological Theory EPUB](https://www.academia.edu/40368858/An_Unauthorized_Companion_to_American_Archaeological_Theory_EPUB) (Accessed 24 January 2024).

This book is a fantastic, fast-paced introduction to archaeological theory. It is intended to be read in tandem with an archaeological theory course, and in recommending it here I assume that you are getting a heavy dose of theory in your other master's-level modules. We are reading the preface and first two chapters as part of this module, but the rest of the book covers various theoretical approaches in more detail. Fogelin has also VERY HELPFULLY prepared initial reading lists on core bodies of theory, ranging from agency to embodiment to queer archaeology. I highly recommend skimming through these lists to see what might be useful for your own project and research interests. The other great thing about this volume is that it is free to download as both an [E-PUB](#) and a [pdf](#), as part of a laudable experiment in open-access publishing that Fogelin has reflected upon in the [Society for American Archaeology Archaeological Record](#).

Kelsky, K. (2015). *The Professor Is In: The Essential Guide to Turning Your PhD into a Job*. New York: Three Rivers Press.

When I was coming up, this was the quintessential guide to the academic job market, written by a cultural anthropologist who received tenure and then pivoted to marketing job market advice to grad students. Her book provides brass tacks descriptions of the expectations, job documents, and processes typical of the academic job search. Though it is geared towards American audiences, her advice about the structure and nature of job documents is generally sound.

Newport, C. (2016) [Deep work: rules for focused success in a distracted world](#), London, Piatkus.

I read this book when searching for strategies to improve my own work-life balance. Newport is an Associate Professor of Computer Science at Georgetown University in the USA, so comes at issues of focus with an understanding of academic workloads and mindsets. The book doesn't critically engage with cultural and historical understandings of productivity or academic value, but it does provide a useful framework for interrogating your own work structures and practices.

Olson, K. (20) Advice for Graduate Students. <https://www.olsonkg.com/advice-for-graduate-students>

This website, run by a colleague who teaches at Washington University in St. Louis, has some great advice for graduate students, covering key books, scholarly skills, reading, writing, organization, and relationships with supervisors.

Silvia, P. (2018). *How to write a lot: a practical guide to productive academic writing*, 2nd edn. Washington D.C., American Psychological Association.

This is another book I read while thinking through my own writing practices. [Silvia](#) is another academic—a Professor of Psychology at the University of North Carolina, Greensboro, and so is well-positioned to provide a useful perspective on academic writing. I found this a quick, snappy, engaging read. If you benefit from co-working and collective strategies for ensuring accountability, one chapter you may find of particular interest is his guide to starting a writing group (Chapter 4).

Strunk, W., and White, E.B. (1979). [The elements of style](#), 3rd edn. New York, MacMillan Publishing.

The quintessential old school guide to strong, clear writing. Should you need a more illustrious recommendation, it's on Stephen King's list of resources for writers who want to improve their craft. You can find cheap used copies online or at many second-hand bookstores.